

Results and Discussion

Morpholine: Morpholine acted as an excellent corrosion inhibitor for brass particularly at a concentration of $2.3 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power increased with increase in its concentrations. Inhibition was practically independent of the duration of the exposure. The galvanostatic measurements showed that in the case of morpholine, the cathodic polarization was remarkable, the anodic polarization being negligible. There was a sudden jump in cathodic polarization between the current density values 4.0 to 5.0×10^{-3} amp/cm². The inhibition is predominantly under cathodic control.

Piperidine: Piperidine gave an excellent inhibition at its lowest concentration i.e., $2.0 \times 10^{-2} M$. Its efficiency was found to be independent of its concentration as well as the duration of the exposure. The galvanostatic measurements showed that cathodic polarization was more significant than the anode polarization. At current density value between 5.0×10^{-3} to 7.5×10^{-3} amp/cm², there was a sudden jump in cathodic polarization. The trend in the polarization suggests that the inhibition is under cathodic control.

Quinoline: Quinoline is acted as a poor corrosion inhibitor for 63/37 brass in $0.1 M K_2S_2O_8$ solution. It afforded only 36% protection at its highest concentration i.e., $1.69 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power increases with increase in its concentration. The galvanostatic measurements showed that in the presence of quinoline, both the electrodes were polarized. A sudden increase in the cathodic potential above a current density value of 2.0×10^{-3} amp/cm² indicates film formation over the metal surface.

α -Picoline: It afforded 96% protection at its highest concentration, $2.02 \times 10^{-1} M$. Its inhibitive power remarkably increased with increase in its concentrations; but slightly decreased at the duration of 120 min. From the polarization measurements it is clear that α -picoline acted as a cathodic inhibitor.

The relative order of inhibitive efficiency is :

Piperidine > morpholine > α -picoline > quinoline

Morpholine and piperidine are saturated heterocyclic compounds. Piperidine is a better inhibitor than morpholine. This may be partly due to high electron density over the nitrogen in piperidine (pka = 11.22) than that in morpholine (pka = 8.7).

Quinoline gives quite poor inhibition compared to α -picoline, morpholine and piperidine.

The polarization data reveal that the anode is rarely significantly polarized. Cathode polarization is quite predominant. At higher current densities, in most of the cases, a sudden jump in the cathode polarization is observed indicating formation of a film. This suggests that the inhibition by amines is principally under the cathodic control.

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Studies on Sulphonamides. Part II: Preparation of Ethyl-4-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate.

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THE wide range of chemotherapeutic as well as pharmacodynamic properties of sulphonamides¹⁻⁶, Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate⁷, and *s*-Triazinyl derivatives⁹⁻¹¹ have prompted us to prepare Ethyl-4-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate with different aryl substitutions as recorded in Table I

2,4-Dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl phenyl sulphide (I; $R_1 = R_2 = Cl$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$), prepared from the reaction of cyanuric chloride (I; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = Cl$) with thiophenol¹² at 0° , was made to react with ethyl-4-aminobenzoate at 30° - 35° to afford compound (I; $R_1 = Cl$, $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC Ph. NH-$, $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$ which on subsequent treatment with excess ammonia in dioxan medium furnished the corresponding 2-amino compound. The product thus obtained was refluxed with different arylsulphonyl chloride to give the corresponding sulphonamides which were finally oxidised to respective sulphones.

Experimental

(a) 2,4-Dichloro-*s*-triazin-6-yl phenyl sulphide (I; $R_1 = R_2 = Cl$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

To cyanuric chloride (I; $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = Cl$) (18.45 g.) in acetone (30 ml) kept at 0° , a solution of thiophenol (11 g.) in acetone (15 ml.) was gradually added with constant stirring followed by addition of aqueous sodium hydroxide (100 ml. 4%). The reaction mixture was stirred for half an hour and poured in crushed ice. The product obtained was

filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 23.22 g. (90.00%) m.p. 72°-73°.

(b) *Ethyl-4'-(2-chloro-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Ethyl-4-aminobenzoate (8.250 g.) dissolved in dioxan (25 ml.) was added to the suspension of (compound I; $R_1 = R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = S-C_6H_5$) (12.90 g.) in dioxan (25 ml.) at 30° to 35°. The contents were stirred for an hour with the gradual addition of an aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (10 ml.; 20%) and subsequently poured in crushed ice. The product was isolated as usual and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 18.5 g. (95.72%) m.p. 168°-70°. (Found: N, 14.40%, $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N_4S$ required: N, 14.49%).

(c) *Ethyl-4'-(2-amino-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = NH_2$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Liquor ammonia (50 ml.) was added to the solution of (compound I; $R_1 = Cl$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (18 g.) in dioxan and refluxed in water bath at 80°-85° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured in crushed ice, product was isolated as usual and crystallised from ethanol. Yield 15.0 g. (87.78%) m.p. 140°-42° (Found: N, 19.00% $C_{18}H_{17}O_2N_5S$ requires: N, 19.07%).

(d) *Ethyl-4'-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylthio-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$):

Compound (I; $R_1 = NH_2$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (0.01 mole) dissolved in acetone was added to the solution of arylsulphonyl chloride (0.01 mole) in pyridine and heated under reflux on water bath at 80°-85° for 1½ hr. The contents were poured into crushed ice and clear solution obtained was acidified by dilute hydrochloric acid (congo red). The product obtained after the addition of aqueous sodium acetate solution (10 ml.; 8%) was filtered, washed, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of these compounds are recorded in the Table.

(e) *Ethyl-4'-(2-arylsulphonamido-4-phenylsulphonyl-s-triazin-6-yl)-aminobenzoate* (I; $R_1 = -NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = -SO_2-C_6H_5$):

Compound (I; $R_1 = -NH-SO_2-R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$; $R_3 = S-C_6H_5$) (1 g.) was dissolved in acetone and glacial acetic acid (10 ml.). To this potassium permanganate solution (6%) was added gradually with constant stirring at room temperature till its colour persisted and kept for 3-4 hrs. The contents were decolourised by passing sulphurdioxide gas. The product obtained was poured in crushed ice, filtered, washed with cold water, dried and crystallised from ethanol. Physical constants of the compounds are recorded in the Table.

TABLE—PHYSICAL DATA OF SULPHONAMIDES OF STRUCTURE (I)

Sr. No.	R	$R_1 = NH-SO_2R$; $R_2 = H_5C_2OOC\ Ph.NH-$		$R_3 = S-C_6H_5$		$R_3 = SO_2-C_6H_5$	
		Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C	Yield %	m.p. °C
1.	Phenyl	65.34	125-27	72.73	232-34		
2.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	70.00	110-12	68.15	226-28		
3.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	60.00	105-07	65.00	195-96		
4.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	65.80	190-93	69.80	198-200		
5.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	59.00	97-98	64.00	210-12		
6.	<i>p</i> -Iodophenyl	68.40	108-09	68.00	190-92		
7.	<i>p</i> -Acetamidophenyl	62.30	135-37	71.00	178-80		
8.	α -Naphthyl	63.70	95-97	78.00	203-05		
9.	β -Naphthyl	57.30	100-02	80.00	186-88		

All the above compounds gave correct N analysis.

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Chemical Investigation of some Mangrove Species. Part II: *Carapa obovata* Bl.

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C. OBOVATA Bl. is a small tree with a large spherical fruit (Bengali: Dhundul). This mangrove genus *Carapa* belongs to family Meliaceae.